

CRITICAL UNDERSTANDING OF INDIAN ECONOMY, GLOBALISATION, AND POVERTY

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Abstract

It is an attempt to study the economic growth story of India. In the present context the debate on neoliberal policies is growing in India. The economic reforms were essential after independence. The pro poor people of India had expectations towards the economic reforms to alleviate poverty. This reform with the agenda of economic growth was in terms of only GDP. It favoured not only upper class rich people but also to middle class people. These people are very few but they crushed the opportunities of large section of poor people. This paper looks at these discussions and raise concern for importance of social opportunities and equal distribution of wealth in all sections of society.

Key Terms

Neoliberal policies, Liberalization, State socialism, Social Opportunities, Economic Development, Social Variables

Objectives:

- To study the economic scenario of the India.
- To study the thoughts of Ambedkar on 'State Socialism'

Research Methodology

The qualitative research methodology is used to study this research. The descriptive research methodology with census method is used. The focus group discussion with all 30 social work faculties and staff members of DNCVP's College of Social Work, Jalgaon was the primary qualitative data. The informal interview method was used for data collection. The secondary sources of data collection were collected mostly from writing and speeches of Dr. Ambedkar and other literature was referred.

Private corporate sector-led growth

Huge working population involved in the sectors with very low income. A very small population is working in the booming sectors. Different sectors are missing the linkage in between. It reflected as the backwardness and poverty in society. As the private corporate sectors are growing faster, the gap is increasing in rich and poor.

The high growth rate phenomenon is externally induced one. It is dependent on the large capital inflow from developed countries to India. The increased integration of the Indian economy with global economy created the chances for crisis, shock and stagnation. Imperialistic power is exercised by the developed countries over Indian economy.

Foreign capital inflows generated boom in the credit. It shapes Indian economic structure. Consumer has choice for the better off choice. The concentration for better choices increased. The demands for the same increased. It led in to growth in range of industries for catering demands of consumers. This market remains narrow. Then it pushed for rapid growth on the narrow base. It essentially separated from rest of economy. It created a large section of the elite class from the society. It worked in the form of SEZ, BPO industries etc.

State is working for transporting surplus to the private corporate sector. The article put forth issue of massive subsidising to the private corporate sector and increasing privation. It talks about increasing inequality with great threat to social order of society. It produces the conditions where foreign investor will get maximum returns. The Indian economy will remain hollow space.

The solution for the neoliberal strategies is suggested in the last of article. The growth based on agriculture will be the solution for current economic policies. It will interlink different economic sector. This type of economic growth will depend on internal dynamics. It is important because it will help to bring suppressed social forces in to the process of development.

Indian economy

Indian government caught in dilemma of 2 paradigms. These are political and economic development of India. Since, 1980's India had adopted neoliberal policies. These two paradigms are conflicting with each other and bringing contradictions in needs, commitment, political will and finances. In such dilemma, citizens do not know anything about outcome of their demands and expectations.

In political paradigm, the different radical groups and new political formations are forcing new expectations & demands on Government. These new political groups are promoting an ideology as "Social Justice". The depressed caste and class of society are supporting to such political groups. This group has very limited impact on development policies. The policy framework should focus on socioeconomic realities e.g. caste dynamics, rampant poverty, multilayered deprivation and emancipation of marginalised social groups including women.

In terms of economic development paradigm problem lies in commitment of Government's neoliberal policies. It focuses on economic and institutional

planning. That created not only conflict but also contradictions to political and social policies. "Welfarist" model of development is politically and socially advisable. The new problem is rising now days in form of "Institutional Decline". It suggests that inefficiency in the governance of Government institutions.

The government commitments in form of socio-political and economic terms are not fully achieved. The government has shown its commitment to social development through NREGS, Right to Information Act & Women Reservation Bill. At same time, India has accepted 'Millennium Development Goal'. It shows Government's commitment to global economic paradigm. This creates the difficult situation for the common citizen of India. Citizen cannot think about their demand and commitments in such atmosphere.

Government is allowing radical group of citizens to involve in decision making and implementation process. They called it as the participatory model. This model is not working because unresolved social problems like caste discrimination, class differences and strong patriarchy of society. This questioned on the participatory model. The conflict situation of the government is explored in detail by focusing more light on budgetary allocation and delivery system of it.

As inadequate expenditure of central government on the social service sectors had created inequality, unethical activities, demoralising youth and violence in the society. The middle class of society got the benefits from the provisions of budget but marginalised large section of society is dissatisfied with all neoliberal policies. So in this context, we observed that Thatcherist model of economic development is not working. Dr. Ambedkar had the vision for Indian economic development. Hence it is essential to study of Dr. Ambedkar's philosophy of economic development for India.

State socialism

Ambedkar was a social democrat. He believed in state and its role in the economic development process. He had given the economic manifesto in his one of the book "States & Minorities". He talked about the united states of India. He did not give any right of secession in the proposed model. He called it "State Socialism". His ideas were revolving around separate electorates, separate village settlements and strong measures against social boycott of untouchable. He was in favour nationalisation of basic industries. He was in favour of nationalisation of land. He talked about the collectives of farming.¹

Ambedkar had a dream of social and economic justice. He said that any future government could not get goal of socioeconomic justice unless it accept the socialist economy. He described the taxation policy. The person's 'taxable capacity' should be the criteria for levying taxes. He was against the 'criteria of income' for paying tax. The tax should pay more by the rich people. He expected elasticity in land revenue. The all classes are fairly treated for taxation system. Further he talked about the raising finances for the state. Ambedkar suggested that to reduce

expenditure on army, abolition of prohibition and saving of the excise revenue and insurance nationalisation to all state & private employees.

Dr. Ambedkar was in favour of industrial development. Industries should maintain at socially desirable level. He thought of industrial development with basic right of every individual to share in that wealth for decent and dignified existence. He asked to devise means which can assure individuals against insecurity.

Essential Need of Current Economic Policy's Debates

In India economic reforms are well discussed. The both sides have the acrid, forceful and firm arguments. Amartya & Jean in their writing of "Well beyond liberalisation" talks beyond issue of economic reforms in their present forms. He was saying that in India lots of energy is spending on attacking and defending on central policy reform. But in doing so we are missing the broader view of social opportunities. The central issue for argument should expand social opportunities open to people.

Debate should revolve around importance of creation and use of 'social opportunities' than of 'freeing' of market. India has ineffective and an insufficiency government activity in basic education, health care, social security, land reform and promotion of social change. This reflected as in widespread deprivation, economic stagnation and social inequality. He had given solution where he says that it is essential to improve government activities and public action. That will help to free the Indian economy from the current debates. He discussed the market- complementary and market-excluding government activities. He asks for the radical change.

Conclusion

In the contemporary world of globalisation, India has accepted neoliberal policies. Indian economy is not an agricultural economy but it is industrial economy. It has no control of state and it has not social desire to sustain society. State is under the control of capitalist. The world's famous millionaires are in this country where as more than 200 million of poor population is also living in this country.

Indian government is in favour of upper and middle class which are affluent. All policies are designed which are in favour of them. Poor people or marginal people of this country alienate to Indian economic system. The ultimate result of which is in the form farmer suicide and strong assertion of Naxalite movement.

Industrial development without distribution of wealth in the community will not help to the objective of development. The objective of industrial development is to alleviate poverty of Indian marginal population. The role of state is very important in this context. The primary beneficiaries of the development should be community but the all neoliberal policies are in favour of corporatist. The global economic politics is building pressure on India which is executed by different agencies as World Bank, IMF, WTO, UNAID and UNDP etc. They had set up

“Millennium Development Goals” (MDP).

The developing country like India has accepted their goals for the development. India could not resolve the issues of caste and tribe identity since its independence. It is an alarm sign for the Indian government to be in the favour of few rich people against the benefit of large marginal section of society. India is marching towards repetition of history. We had history of colonisation. Now our fast track economic growth indicates we are becoming the corporatist government.

The budget documents of Indian government are always in complex language. The common man could not read it. The progressive debates on political, social, economical and cultural level never thought of. The parliament houses are infamous for their unconstitutional behaviour. The weak political will without any strong ideology is the feature of Indian democracy. The lack of vision of political parties and their leaders led us to an urge of economic crisis in India. Corruption at judiciary, executive, media and legislative systems are hindering state to become “State of Socialism”.

The thoughts of Dr. Ambedkar forced us to think beyond ‘for and against’ discussion of economic policies of Indian government. The focus of policy debate should come through the perspective of social and economic deprived people. It is the time for revolution in the

terminologies of discussions and debate in the form of radical change.

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